

HYDROPROCESSING MODELLING TOOLKIT FOR PROCESS DESIGN

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ABSTRACT: Hydroprocessing of biomass-derived fast pyrolysis oils is an efficient way of producing bio-intermediates that could be introduced into existing refinery systems. Bio-oil is a complex mixture of oxygenated hydrocarbons and only the ultimate analysis is completely detectable. Modelling of the hydrotreating process requires extensive data regarding bio-compounds' conversion, yields and their interactions. Pyrolysis bio-oil data can range from ultimate analysis, model compounds / detailed analysis and/or compound grouping based on functional groups. Similarly, the experimental results for the hydrotreated oil can also include a range of diverse data in nature and complexity. This work presents the development of an engineering design toolkit for bio-oil hydroprocessing design that can produce mass & energy balance results incorporating a mix of methodologies that correspond to the three types of potential available data. This toolkit is built in the Aspen Plus software and could be readily used for process design and systems integration purposes.

Keywords: biorefinery, modelling, upgrading.

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, there is a growing interest in producing biofuels from lignocellulosic sources or bio-crudes that could be readily inserted into existing refinery infrastructures. In particular, the advantages of the latter are attributed to the fact that co-processing could reduce the cost of producing biofuels, since the infrastructure already exists, and there is no need for engine modifications, since the produced fuel is indistinguishable from conventional fuels.

Fast pyrolysis is an attractive, relatively inexpensive thermochemical process that produces bio-oil as the main liquid product [1]. Pyrolysis bio-oils are complex mixtures of more than 300 identified oxygenated hydrocarbons that have high oxygen (35-40 wt%) and water contents (15-30 wt%). The sonorous presence of water and oxygen render bio-oils thermally unstable, corrosive and immiscible with hydrocarbon fuels [2].

Therefore, reducing these contents is necessary before inserting into existing refinery systems. The individual steps of a thermochemical, hydroprocessing-based biorefinery are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Steps of a hydroprocessing-based biorefinery.

Hydroprocessing is an upgrading process that utilizes hydrogen for the removal of the oxygen heteroatoms and aims at bio-oil's overall oxygen to carbon ratio reduction.

It is an exothermic reaction usually conducted at temperatures between 200-400 °C, pressures between 100-250 bar and with large excess of H₂ [3]. Most common hydrotreating catalysts are based on Co and Ni

as well as on noble metals such as Ru and Pd [4]. The hydroprocessing reactor outlet consists of an organic, an aqueous and a gaseous phase that contains the unreacted H₂. A large number of reactions are involved in hydroprocessing and the most common are: hydrogenation, hydrodeoxygenation, decarboxylation / decarbonylation as well as cracking and hydrocracking.

The contained oxygen is removed as H₂O and/or in the form of CO₂, CO and other carbon-containing gases [4]. Extensive cracking and hydrocracking occurs at high temperatures and is undesirable due to the degradation of the large hydrocarbon chains to light gases and carbon [5]. In addition, polymerization reactions and coke formation are taking place at higher temperatures leading to catalyst deactivation and reactor fouling [6]. As a consequence, hydrotreating is a medley of diverse occurring reactions with a reaction mechanism still under research [5], [7], [8].

Accurate modelling and simulation of the hydrotreating process could facilitate the design of new processes and enable the cost-effective integration of bio-oil hydrotreating (HDT) in the market. However, HDT modelling is a challenge due to the diversity and plethora of occurring reactions. The product distribution and occurring reactions of the contained chemical compounds vary based on the reaction conditions [9], [10]. Moreover, the bio-oil mixture contains a palette of numerous oxygenated compounds of multiple functional groups such as acids, aldehydes, phenols, furans etc. Each chemical group behaves differently during hydrotreating, whereas possible interactions between the groups are not ruled out [11].

Due to their complexity, bio-oils cannot be completely identified using one analytical method and must be subjected to a combination of analytical techniques. Therefore, the available experimental data are diverse in nature and complexity. They can range from ultimate analyses [6], [12], model compounds / detailed analyses [12], [13] and/or compound grouping based on functional groups or properties [8], [14]. Similarly, the experimental results for the hydrotreated oil can also include diverse types of data. As a consequence, hydrotreating modelling efforts are based on the type of available experimental data. Each type has to represent the complexity of the bio-oil and upgraded oil as simple

as possible, but with respect to the mass and energy balances of the mixture.

This work classifies the available experimental data into three groups that can be used for HDT modelling purposes. Moreover, it presents the on-going development of an engineering design toolkit for bio-oil hydroprocessing that can produce mass and energy balance results incorporating a mix of methodologies/approaches that correspond to the three types of available experimental data. This toolkit is built in Aspen Plus and could be readily used for process design and system integration purposes. Choosing one of these approaches depends on the process simulation targets and the available experimental data.

2 MODELLING METHODOLOGIES

The three investigated modeling approaches are based on the types of available experimental data. The Aspen Plus modelling methodology is described for each case hereafter.

2.1 Ultimate analysis approach

The first modelling approach is based on the ultimate analysis of the bio-oil and upgraded oil, which are 100 % known. It implies that only the C, H, O, N content of the reactor inlet and outlet are taken into consideration as well as the yield of each product phase (organic, aqueous and gaseous).

In that case the hydroprocessing reactor is modelled using an Aspen Plus RYield reactor model. The bio-oil, hydrotreated oil as well as the aqueous phase streams are represented as non-conventional streams, where the ultimate analysis is the main input/output of the streams.

The atomic and total mass balances as well as the energy balances were implemented in Fortran subroutines, whereas the upgraded oil composition was calculated by ensuring that the inlet and outlet mass balances are in agreement.

2.2 Model compounds approach

Detailed product distributions are available in literature but due to the complexity, diversity and multitude of the contained compounds, it is impossible to use them in commercial process simulation software, such as Aspen Plus [13]. Therefore, this complexity should be reduced to a smaller, manageable number of compounds with respect to the oil's chemistry and energy content. To this end, the second modelling approach represents the complex chemistry of bio-oil by a mixture of water and a number of organic compounds.

Past modelling efforts using this approach refer to the simulation of a complete pyrolysis and hydrotreating-based biorefinery using 83 model compounds and their reactions [15], whereas Atsonios et al. [16] studied the integration of different hydroprocessing concepts utilizing bio-oils from diverse biomass sources. The difficulties associated with this modelling approach lie within the selection and utilization of appropriate hydroprocessing literature data. The available experimental efforts study one or a limited number of model compounds at a time, which is appropriate to make rough assumptions regarding the fate of the component throughout the reaction. But this strategy does not determine the possible interactions between the contained components of the mixture, which could lead to

misleading conclusions that do not capture the broad picture of the process. Therefore, there is a shortage of available experimental data that can be used for modelling purposes.

The bio-oil stream is assumed to be represented by water and a mixture of some components with the highest concentration among the detectable compounds. The concentration of each compound is calculated by ensuring that the atomic mass balances of the bio-oil, and the model-stream are in agreement. Since the bio-oil stream does not have the same heating value as the model-stream, an RYield is interpolated between the initial bio-oil stream and the model-stream in order to correct any heat-balance inconsistencies. Subsequently, the model-compounds stream enters the hydroprocessing reactor, which is represented by an RStoic reactor model.

A possible reaction network has to be implemented into the model with respect to the reaction pathways and reactivity of each compound [17]. For more detailed investigations, hydrotreating kinetic data can be implemented, if available.

2.3 Compound grouping approach

The third approach classifies the bio-oil mixture based on functional groups or common properties. This approach is already known from petrochemical applications, where crude oil is "lumped" based on distillation cuts and each lump is simulated as distinct species. Similarly, in hydrotreating applications, bio-oil is grouped based on common properties. Elliott et al. [14], for instance, grouped the bio- and upgraded-oil based on their chemical groups, whereas Garcia-Perez et al. [18] grouped bio-oil based on the solubility differences of each fraction.

The Aspen Plus modelling methodology of this approach is similar to the model compounds approach. An RYield reactor is interpolated before the HDT reactor to "lump" the bio-oil ultimate analysis into the grouped-component species. These pseudo-components are solely defined based on their molecular weights and functional groups.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Ultimate Analysis Approach

The reactor inlet stream, consisting of bio-oil and H₂, is fed into the hydroprocessing reactor. This modelling approach is based only on the ultimate analysis of the bio- and upgraded-oil streams. The bio-oil properties are based on [12] and product yields on the work conducted by [19].

Figure 2 illustrates the total mass balances around the hydroprocessing reactor and the mass fractions of each phase. The reactor outlet consists of the upgraded-oil fraction, the aqueous phase, which contains a considerable amount of carbon, and the gaseous phase which contains the unreacted H₂ and other carbon containing gases, such as CO₂, CO, CH₄, etc.

Table I shows the calculated ultimate analysis of the initial bio-oil stream compared to the hydrotreated oil.

The oxygen to carbon ratio, as well as the moisture content of the oil are reduced, which are the main targets of this upgrading process in order to be fed into a conventional refinery.

Figure 2: Mass balance around the HDT reactor.

Table I: Ultimate analysis of bio- and hydrotreated-oils.

Ultimate Analysis (wt. %)	Bio-Oil	Treated-Oil
C	54.5	73.5
H	7.0	8.0
O	37.9	18.1
N	0.6	0.4
H ₂ O	24.0	7.7
O/C	0.695	0.246

This modelling approach simulates accurately the elemental mass and energy balances around the hydroprocessing reactor. It is suitable for engineering calculations such as for estimating the C, H, O, N content of each phase as well as for determining hydrogen consumption of the process. However, it fails to determine the oil's chemistry, compounds and kinetics or rates, which makes it unsuitable for more detailed investigations of the process.

3.2 Model Compounds Approach

The model compounds approach uses the bio-oil ultimate analysis for conversion to a mixture of compounds with the highest concentration among the detectable components [12], [13]. This conversion has to be consistent regarding the mass and energy content of the bio- and model-feed. Furthermore, a possible reaction network of 54 possible reactions was constructed and incorporated into the model [15], [20]–[23]. Figure 3 presents the on-going work and modelling methodology of the model compounds approach.

Using this approach, chemistry and compound rates are accurate. In addition, if kinetics models are available, they can be implemented into the model. However, due to the assumption that a complex mixture of compounds is represented by a certain number of compounds, atomic mass balance closure cannot be attained and therefore this method is not appropriate for engineering calculations.

3.3 Component Groups Approach

The component-groups modelling approach is based on the work conducted by Shemfe et al. [10]. In that work, bio-oil was “lumped” based on each fraction's volatility and kinetic data from [24] were utilized to represent the hydrotreating reactions. In this work, the grouping procedure was based on the work conducted by Elliott et al. [10] who grouped the bio- and upgraded-oil in groups based on their chemical function. Table 2 illustrates the preliminary results of the modelling.

Figure 3: Methodology and on-going work on the model-compounds approach.

Table II: Component Groups (wt.%) of bio- and hydrotreated-oils.

Component Groups (wt.%)	Bio-Oil	Treated-Oil
Guaiacols	26.8	7.7
Aldehydes & Ketones	12.5	3.0
Furans	5.5	5.6
Acids & Esters	13.5	8.9
Phenols & alkyl-Phenols	8.1	4.3
Alcohols & Polyols	8.5	15.7
Alkanes	0.0	23.7
Aromatics	0.0	31.2

This approach is a compromise between the first and second approach with some extent of accurate mass and energy balances and some extent of detailed chemistry of the mixtures.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This work presents a hydroprocessing modeling toolkit, which is based on the three types of available experimental data in literature. The first tool is based on the ultimate analysis of the bio-oil and hydrotreated-oil and is suitable for accurate mass and energy balance calculations of the process. The second tool uses the model-compounds approach and is suitable for calculations, where oil chemistry is important and there are experimental data available for each compound. The third approach groups bio-oil into functional groups and is a compromise of the first two approaches.

Development of detailed and/or prediction models of the hydrotreating process would require detailed experimental analyses that study the evolution of each

component or component groups throughout the process.

Therefore, future work will include the conduction of hydroprocessing experiments at the CERTH hydrotreating plant and utilization of the experimental data for HDT modeling purposes.

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